

Semantic Communication Robustness Under Imperfect Channel State Information

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Abstract—This paper investigates semantic robustness under imperfect channel state information (CSI) in an end-to-end semantic communication system. We consider a unified semantic model that includes knowledge-graph representation, relation-aware GNN semantic encoding, and transmission over a 3GPP TR 38.901 TDL-B-100 fading channel with multipath and noise. This framework enables the evaluation of semantic performance under practical wireless impairments. Our numerical results show how semantic communication schemes enhance robustness to outdated or unreliable CSI, enabling more graceful performance degradation while preserving task-relevant information even under imperfect CSI.

Index Terms—Semantic communications, knowledge graph encoding, OFDM, imperfect CSI, semantic robustness

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution toward artificial intelligence (AI)-native wireless networks is changing the objective of communication system design. In many emerging applications, the receiver is not interested in perfect symbol recovery, but in the recovery of task-relevant information. This shift motivates semantic communication, where performance is evaluated by semantic correctness [1]–[3].

This perspective is particularly relevant for knowledge-centric applications, in which the transmitted message is naturally structured and the receiver is interested in concepts and relations rather than in symbol-by-symbol reconstruction. Knowledge graphs are a suitable representation in this case because they jointly describe entities and their relations in a compact form [4]. As a result, relation-aware processing is expected to better preserve message intent when dependencies among nodes must be reconstructed at the receiver.

Recent work in semantic communications addresses different aspects of embedding, transmitting, and interpreting meaning in wireless systems. In [5], semantic meta-split learning is proposed, in which devices transmit smashed features and gradients at a cut layer; the transmitter-side model acts as the semantic encoder and the receiver-side model acts as the semantic decoder. In [6], semantic structures are captured through orthogonally decomposed latent subspaces, and the transmitted content is adapted to downstream tasks such as reconstruction or inference, improving task-oriented efficiency.

Another research direction focuses on semantic mismatch across agents. The work in [7] models transformations between

semantic domains using optimal transport to align received representations with the receiver domain. Building on this idea, [8] models language mismatch through an Markov decision process (MDP) framework to account for semantic- and task-level mismatch errors. Multi-user semantic alignment is further considered in [9], where a common transmitter-side semantic encoder is combined with local receiver-side semantic equalizers to support heterogeneous agents under complexity and power constraints. In [10], a relative-representation framework and Parseval frame-based processing are used to enable semantic equalization with linear, well-conditioned transforms and reduced complexity overhead.

Despite these advances, an important gap remains between semantic-layer design and realistic wireless propagation. Most existing works focus on semantic representation, latent alignment, or task-level metric, while giving limited attention to multipath fading, frequency selectivity, and channel-estimation errors in the end-to-end chain. As a result, the robustness of semantic communication under practical physical-layer impairments is still not well investigated.

To address this point, semantic communication should be evaluated together with a detailed wireless channel and explicit imperfect-channel state information (CSI) models. In particular, it is important to understand whether semantic representations are inherently more robust to channel-estimation mismatch than *classical* transmission.

Motivated by this problem, in this paper we study semantic robustness under imperfect CSI in an end-to-end semantic communication chain. We expand on the graph-based semantic communication chain introduced in [4] and use it as the reference architecture to evaluate robustness under imperfect CSI. Assuming that semantic representations are more robust to channel-estimation mismatch because they preserve structural redundancy and task-oriented information. In contrast to symbol-centric transmission, the semantic decoder may still recover the intended meaning under residual equalization distortion.

The contributions of this work include the following:

- We evaluate a semantic communication chain in which outdated and unreliable CSI is modeled to capture dynamic physical-layer conditions that may degrade the end-to-end performance of semantic encoding and decoding over orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) transmissions in multipath fading and noisy

Fig. 1. System model under imperfect CSI. The pipeline includes knowledge-graph input, LLM feature extraction, GNN semantic encoding, joint semantic channel encoding and decoding with graph-level mode selection, OFDM transmission, and semantic reconstruction.

environments. This enables direct analysis of semantic performance under practical channel conditions.

- We introduce a criterion for semantic mode adaptation that combines task performance and semantic symbol efficiency. This enables dynamic semantic mode selection across channel conditions.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the semantic and channel models. Section III introduces the semantic-mode adaptation criterion. Section IV reports numerical results and discussion. Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model considered in this paper is depicted in Fig. 1. Specifically, we adopt a knowledge-graph-based representation of semantic messages [4], which provides a structured description of entities and their interactions and facilitates efficient encoding of contextual and task-relevant information. The graph is then encoded into node-wise latent vectors, mapped to complex symbols with power normalization, and transmitted over an OFDM system. Although this is an operational choice, the overall framework is also applicable to other semantic message representations. In the following, we describe each component of the system model.

A. Semantic Chain

1) *Knowledge Graph*: We represent the system input as a knowledge graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{E})$, where $\mathcal{N} = \{n_i\}_{i=1}^{N_e}$ is the set of node descriptors and $\mathcal{E} = \{r_{j,i}\}$ is the set of directed

relation descriptors, with $r_{j,i}$ denoting the relation from node j to node i .

2) *Feature Extractor*: The feature-extractor block is implemented with a large language model (LLM), mapping node and relation text descriptors to latent space vectors as

$$\mathbf{v}_i = f_{\text{LLM}}(n_i), \quad \mathbf{e}_{j,i} = f_{\text{LLM}}(r_{j,i}). \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{v}_i and $\mathbf{e}_{j,i}$ denote the initial node and relation embeddings, respectively. We denote by \mathcal{V}_n and \mathcal{R} the node and relation vocabularies.

3) *Semantic Encoder*: The semantic-encoder block is a relation-aware GNN that compresses graph semantics into node-wise embeddings. Following a graph isomorphism network (GIN)-style message-passing update,

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i = g_{\Theta} \left((1 + \epsilon) \mathbf{v}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \text{ReLU}(\mathbf{v}_j + \mathbf{e}_{j,i}) \right), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(i)$ denotes the neighbors of node i , $g_{\Theta}(\cdot)$ is a trainable neural mapping, and ϵ is a trainable scalar. Each output embedding satisfies $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\lambda}}$, where d_{λ} denotes the semantic latent dimension. The resulting latent set $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = \{\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i\}_{i=1}^{N_e}$ is passed to the semantic-channel transmit block.

4) *Joint Semantic Channel Encoder + Modulator*: Given graph-level mode selection $m \in \mathcal{M}$ for one transmission step, the joint semantic channel encoder and modulator maps the semantic embedding to complex symbols:

$$\mathbf{s}_i^{(m)} = f_{\text{ch}}^{(m)}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i). \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mathbf{s}_i^{(m)}$ denotes the transmitted symbol vector associated with node i under mode m . The detailed mode-dependent processing into subcarriers is presented in Subsection II-B.

5) *Joint Semantic Channel Decoder + Demodulator*: After channel propagation and equalization (Subsection II-B), the receiver-side joint semantic channel decoder and demodulator reconstructs semantic latents from the equalized symbols as

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i = f_{\text{ch}}^{-1, (m)}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(m)}). \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(m)}$ is the equalized symbol vector associated with node i under mode m .

6) *Semantic Decoder*: The semantic-decoder block infers node identities as

$$\mathbf{z}_i = f_{\text{node}}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i), \quad \hat{n}_i = \arg \max_{u \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{V}_n\}} [\text{softmax}(\mathbf{z}_i)]_u, \quad (5)$$

and reconstructs relations by jointly processing node-pair embeddings,

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_j, \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i) = f_{\text{tr}}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_j, \hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i), \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{r}_{j,i} = \arg \max_{\ell \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{R}\}} [\text{softmax}(f_{\text{rel}}(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_j, \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i))]_{\ell}. \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{z}_i is the node-logit vector for node i , $f_{\text{node}}(\cdot)$ maps reconstructed latent vectors to node logits, $f_{\text{tr}}(\cdot, \cdot)$ generates pairwise transformed features, and $f_{\text{rel}}(\cdot, \cdot)$ outputs relation logits over the relation vocabulary \mathcal{R} .

7) *Reconstructed KG*: The final output is the reconstructed knowledge graph $\hat{\mathcal{G}} = (\hat{\mathcal{N}}, \hat{\mathcal{E}})$ with node and relation predictions obtained from the semantic decoder. For training, we combine reconstruction losses and mutual-information regularization through

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}^{\text{node}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}^{\text{rel}} - \alpha I(\mathbf{\Lambda}; \hat{\mathbf{\Lambda}}), \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{\Lambda}} = \{\hat{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_i\}_{i=1}^{N_e}$ is the reconstructed latent set, $I(\mathbf{\Lambda}; \hat{\mathbf{\Lambda}})$ denotes the mutual information between transmitted and reconstructed latent representations, and α controls the mutual-information regularization term. Following the standard two-step training routine, we first calibrate the mutual-information estimator and then optimize the end-to-end model parameters.

B. Channel Model

For a graph transmitted under semantic mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, let q_m be the number of complex symbols used to represent each node under that mode. The selected mode is shared by all nodes in the graph. The joint semantic channel encoder and modulator first applies

$$\mathbf{s}_i^{(m)} = f_{\text{ch}}^{(m)}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i), \quad \mathbf{s}_i^{(m)} \in \mathbb{C}^{q_m}, \quad (9)$$

then concatenates all node symbol vectors into the graph payload

$$\mathbf{s}^{(m)} = \left[(\mathbf{s}_1^{(m)})^{\text{T}}, \dots, (\mathbf{s}_{N_e}^{(m)})^{\text{T}} \right]^{\text{T}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_e q_m}. \quad (10)$$

The graph payload is then partitioned into

$$T_m = \left\lceil \frac{N_e q_m}{N} \right\rceil \quad (11)$$

OFDM symbols. Hence, if $N_e q_m > N$, the graph payload is divided across multiple OFDM symbols, whereas if $N_e q_m < N$, the last OFDM symbol is zero padded. For notational simplicity, the remaining equations are written for a generic OFDM symbol, whose frequency-domain transmit vector is denoted by $\mathbf{x}^{(m)} = [x_0, \dots, x_{N-1}]^{\text{T}} \in \mathbb{C}^N$.

For one N -subcarrier OFDM symbol, the time-domain samples obtained through an N -point inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) are

$$x[n] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x_k e^{j \frac{2\pi k n}{N}}, \quad n = 0, \dots, N-1. \quad (12)$$

Here, x_k denotes the transmitted symbol on subcarrier k ($k = 0, \dots, N-1$). The cyclic prefix is formed by prepending the last N_{cp} samples, with $N_{\text{cp}} \geq L-1$ to preserve circular convolution over an L -tap channel. We assume block fading over one OFDM symbol and standard timing/frequency synchronization.

The discrete-time channel with additive noise is

$$y[n] = \sum_{\ell=0}^{L-1} h[\ell] x[n-\ell] + w[n]. \quad (13)$$

where $h[\ell]$ is the ℓ -th discrete-time channel tap and $w[n]$ is the additive noise sample at time index n . After cyclic prefix (CP) removal and fast Fourier transform (FFT), the received signal on subcarrier k is

$$y_k = h_k x_k + w_k, \quad (14)$$

where w_k is the corresponding frequency-domain noise sample and the subcarrier response is

$$h_k = \sum_{\ell=0}^{L-1} h[\ell] e^{-j \frac{2\pi k \ell}{N}}. \quad (15)$$

For each graph transmission step, $\mathbf{h} = [h[0], \dots, h[L-1]]^{\text{T}}$ is drawn as Rayleigh taps with the corresponding delay-power profile.

Imperfect channel knowledge is modeled in two complementary ways. We assume that the CSI used for equalization is obtained through a feedback-based signaling procedure and may therefore be imperfect or stale. For the CSI-quality experiments of Figs. 2 and 3, channel-estimation mismatch follows [11]:

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}} = \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{csi}}^2} \mathbf{h} + \kappa_{\text{csi}} \tilde{\mathbf{h}}, \quad (16)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}$ is an independent Rayleigh tap vector with the same second-order statistics as \mathbf{h} , and $\kappa_{\text{csi}} \in [0, 1]$ is the CSI mismatch factor, with $\kappa_{\text{csi}} = 0$ corresponding to perfect CSI. For the CSI-aging experiment of Fig. 5, let $a \in \mathbb{N}_0$ denote the CSI age measured as the number of transmitted slots elapsed after CSI acquisition, and let T_{slot} be the slot duration. Following the Jakes model [12], the channel tap vector at age a is modeled as

$$\mathbf{h}^{(a)} = \rho_a \mathbf{h}^{(0)} + \sqrt{1 - \rho_a^2} \check{\mathbf{h}}, \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{h}^{(0)}$ is the channel tap vector at the CSI-acquisition instant, $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}$ is an independent Rayleigh tap vector with the same second-order statistics as $\mathbf{h}^{(0)}$, and ρ_a is the temporal-correlation coefficient given by

$$\rho_a = J_0(2\pi f_D a T_{\text{slot}}), \quad f_D = \frac{v f_c}{c}, \quad (18)$$

with $J_0(\cdot)$ denoting the zeroth-order Bessel function of the first kind, f_D the maximum Doppler frequency, $v = 30$ km/h the user velocity, f_c the carrier frequency, and c the speed of light. In the aging setting, CSI is acquired at age $a = 0$ and then reused after a transmitted slots, so the equalizer operates with the stale estimate associated with $\mathbf{h}^{(0)}$ while the actual channel evolves according to (17). Given \hat{h}_k from the selected CSI model, one-tap MMSE equalization on subcarrier k yields

$$\bar{x}_k = \frac{y_k \hat{h}_k^*}{|\hat{h}_k|^2 + \sigma_w^2}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1. \quad (19)$$

where \bar{x}_k is the equalized estimate of x_k and $\sigma_w^2 = \mathbb{E}[|w_k|^2]$ denotes the noise variance per subcarrier. Since the transmitted symbols are power normalized, we assume $\mathbb{E}[|x_k|^2] = 1$. We adopt one-tap MMSE equalization because it regularizes channel inversion and is the more standard robust choice when noise and CSI mismatch are both present.

Specifically, we consider the 3GPP TR 38.901 TDL-B-100 profile [13]. Then equalized subcarriers yields $\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(m)} = [\bar{x}_0, \dots, \bar{x}_{N-1}]^T$. The joint semantic channel decoder and demodulator then decodes the graph payload into node-wise symbol vectors $\{\bar{\mathbf{s}}_i^{(m)}\}_{i=1}^{N_e}$ and applies $f_{\text{ch}}^{-1, (m)}(\cdot)$ to recover $\hat{\lambda}_i$ for each node i . These reconstructed latent vectors are then processed by the semantic decoder to produce node and relation logits.

III. PROPOSED SEMANTIC MODE ADAPTATION

Outdated or unreliable CSI can severely degrade transmission performance. To fully exploit the benefits of semantic communications under dynamic wireless conditions, we propose a semantic mode adaptation mechanism that jointly adapts the achievable semantic spectral efficiency [14] to the estimated level of CSI unreliability.

To this end, we define a set of semantic transmission modes, each corresponding to a different level of semantic spectral efficiency, *i.e.*, the number of semantic symbols transmitted per second per Hertz. The proposed adaptation mechanism selects the optimal semantic mode based on estimates of current channel conditions (including signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and CSI reliability), by dynamically switching to lower semantic resolution modes when CSI becomes outdated or unreliable, thereby increasing reliance on receiver-side semantic inference.

This approach enables graceful degradation of task performance, rather than the abrupt performance collapse typically observed in classical communication systems.

We adapt the semantic transmission mode according to a task-oriented efficiency metric, *e.g.*, accuracy or F1 score, combining semantic quality and symbol efficiency (See (20)).

For each semantic mode m (defined by semantic latent dimension d_λ and symbol budget q_m), we define:

$$\rho_m(E_s/N_0) = \begin{cases} F_{1,m}(E_s/N_0) r_m, & F_{1,m}(E_s/N_0) \geq F_{1,\text{th}}, \\ 0, & F_{1,m}(E_s/N_0) < F_{1,\text{th}}, \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where $r_m = d_\lambda/q_m$ is the semantic compression rate, interpreted as the number of latent space components conveyed per complex symbol; $F_{1,m}(E_s/N_0)$ is the measured F1 score of mode m at the considered E_s/N_0 ; and $F_{1,\text{th}}$ is the activation threshold. This metric weights task quality by the number of latent components conveyed per symbol.

The selected operating profile is the upper envelope across modes,

$$\rho(E_s/N_0) = \max_m \rho_m(E_s/N_0), \quad (21)$$

which induces the mode-selection rule:

$$m^*(E_s/N_0) = \arg \max_m \rho_m(E_s/N_0). \quad (22)$$

At each transmission step, one mode m^* is selected and applied to all nodes in the current graph. This selection is implemented through a lookup table based on the estimated channel quality.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section evaluates the proposed graph-based semantic communication framework through computer simulations using the system model of Section II. Unless stated otherwise, the wireless link follows the 3GPP TR 38.901 TDL-B-100 channel with additive noise and 3GPP NR numerology $\mu = 0$, corresponding to subcarrier spacing $\Delta f = 15$ kHz and slot duration $T_{\text{slot}} = 1$ ms. The OFDM parameters are $N = 288$ subcarriers and $N_{\text{cp}} = 35$, while the semantic latent dimension is fixed to $d_\lambda = 64$. In our evaluations, the *classical* data-oriented baseline uses Huffman source coding, LDPC channel coding with rate 0.5, and 64-QAM modulation over OFDM. The results are averaged over the WebNLG test set [15] under independently generated channel realizations for 10^3 Monte Carlo simulations. We first analyze robustness versus SNR and CSI-quality mismatch, then study imperfect CSI at high SNR, next examine the semantic-mode adaptation metric, and finally evaluate CSI aging.

We evaluate semantic reconstruction for graph-based semantic messages using the triplet-level F1 score. Let $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{G})$ and $\mathcal{T}(\hat{\mathcal{G}})$ denote the sets of triplets $(n_j, r_{j,i}, n_i)$ in the source and reconstructed graphs, respectively. The F1 score quantifies the balance between precision and recall when identifying correct concept-relation-concept triplets and is defined as

$$F_1 = \frac{2 \text{Precision Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}. \quad (23)$$

Here, precision is the proportion of correctly recovered triplets among all triplets in the reconstructed graph, while recall is the proportion of correctly recovered triplets among all triplets in the source graph. Thus, a triplet is counted as correct only when both endpoint concepts and the relation label are recovered correctly.

Fig. 2. F1 performance versus E_s/N_0 for Semantic and *Classical* transmissions under $\kappa_{csi} \in \{0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3\}$. Filled markers correspond to the semantic scheme, empty markers correspond to the *classical* baseline, and colors indicate the value of κ_{csi} .

First, Fig. 2 shows the F1 score versus E_s/N_0 for the semantic scheme and the *classical* baseline under CSI mismatch factors $\kappa_{csi} \in \{0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3\}$. At very low SNR, neither semantic nor *classical* transmission can survive the noise. As E_s/N_0 increases, however, the semantic scheme improves earlier than the *classical* baseline. For $\kappa_{csi} = 0$, the semantic scheme already reaches an F1 score of about 0.563 at 10 dB and 0.899 at 20 dB, whereas the *classical* baseline remains at 0 up to 10 dB and reaches only about 0.168 at 16 dB. As κ_{csi} increases, the semantic scheme degrades gradually, while the *classical* baseline deteriorates much more abruptly. This indicates that the semantic representation preserves task-relevant structure even before symbol-level recovery becomes reliable. This is why semantic communication has higher robustness to imperfect CSI.

Figure 3 shows the robustness of the semantic chain against channel estimation errors as we evaluate how the performance evolves with κ_{csi} . The semantic scheme starts from an F1 score of about 0.955 at $\kappa_{csi} = 0$ and remains at 0.921 for $\kappa_{csi} = 0.2$ and 0.807 for $\kappa_{csi} = 0.3$. By contrast, the *classical* baseline falls from 1.0 at $\kappa_{csi} = 0$ to about 0.052 at $\kappa_{csi} = 0.2$ and reaches zero from $\kappa_{csi} = 0.3$ onward. This sharp loss shows that, even at high SNR, the *classical* baseline is much more sensitive to CSI mismatch than the semantic scheme. The baseline reaches F1 score 1 at $\kappa_{csi} = 0$ because it explicitly transmits the graph content through source and channel coding, whereas the semantic scheme reconstructs the graph from transmitted latent representations, meaning that a F1 score of 1 for the semantic case could be considered overfitting.

Using the semantic-mode adaptation metric introduced in Section III, Fig. 4 shows $\rho_m(E_s/N_0)$ for four semantic modes with $q_m \in \{2, 4, 8, 16\}$, fixed $d_\lambda = 64$, and activation threshold $F_{1,th} = 0.8$, together with the selected upper envelope $\rho(E_s/N_0)$. Since the threshold is intentionally chosen

Fig. 3. F1 score at $E_s/N_0 = 28$ dB versus CSI quality factor κ_{csi} , comparing the semantic scheme and the *classical* baseline.

Fig. 4. Semantic efficiency metric ρ versus E_s/N_0 for semantic modes with $q_m \in \{2, 4, 8, 16\}$ and fixed semantic latent dimension $d_\lambda = 64$; the black line denotes the selected envelope $\max_m \rho_m$.

to enforce high semantic fidelity, all modes remain inactive up to 12 dB. The first active mode is $q_m = 16$ at 14 dB, followed by $q_m = 8$ in the 16–18 dB region, $q_m = 4$ at 20–24 dB, and finally $q_m = 2$ from 26 dB onward. Therefore, the preferred operating mode moves from conservative symbol allocation to more aggressive compression as the channel improves. This layered activation is consistent with Fig. 2: once semantic reconstruction becomes reliable, higher compression rates can be exploited without sacrificing task performance. Instead of operating with a fixed semantic compression rate, the system can select the mode that maximizes the task-oriented efficiency metric according to (22), thus enabling semantic link adaptation analogous to conventional adaptive modulation and coding, but based on task performance rather than raw throughput.

Finally, Fig. 5 extends the analysis to temporal robustness

Fig. 5. F1 score for semantic and *classical* users versus E_s/N_0 for ages $\{0, 14, 21, 28\}$, where age denotes the number of transmitted slots elapsed after CSI acquisition. Colors and markers indicate age, while solid lines denote the semantic scheme and dashed lines denote the *classical* baseline.

by considering CSI aging, rather than the κ_{csi} -based CSI-quality mismatch used in Figs. 2 and 3. For this experiment, CSI is acquired at age $a = 0$ with $\kappa_{csi} = 0$ and then reused after $a \in \{0, 14, 21, 28\}$ transmitted slots according to (17) and (18), with user velocity $v = 30$ km/h and carrier frequency $f_c = 3.5$ GHz. The semantic results remain tightly grouped across all age values. Around 20 dB, the semantic F1 score ranges from about 0.811 to 0.911, whereas the *classical* baseline ranges from about 0.194 to 0.798. Around 24 dB, the semantic spread is still small, roughly from 0.837 to 0.945, while the *classical* baseline remains much more sensitive to age. Therefore, the proposed semantic framework remains robust not only to instantaneous CSI mismatch but also to CSI staleness.

The results show that the semantic communication framework is more robust than the *classical* baseline under both imperfect and stale CSI. Combined with semantic-mode adaptation, this robustness suggests that practical systems can operate with smaller adaptive safety margins while preserving task performance. This allows us to operate closer to the optimal performance.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we investigated semantic robustness under imperfect CSI in an end-to-end OFDM-based wireless communication framework. Our numerical results show how the semantic-mode adaptation method supports effective switching between semantic modes depending on dynamic channel conditions. The proposed solutions combine knowledge-graph representation and relation-aware GNN semantic encoding, with one-tap MMSE equalization under both CSI mismatch and CSI aging. Our comprehensive numerical evaluation over a 3GPP TR 38.901 tapped-delay-line B (TDL-B)-100 fading channel showed that the semantic messages interpretation is

robust to channel-estimation errors, and degrades more gracefully than *classical* not semantic-empowered communications under CSI staleness. This enables task-oriented link adaptation which is robust to CSI estimation errors, since task-relevant information can still be preserved even when symbol-level recovery is degraded. Future work could investigate multi-user and MIMO semantic communication together with adaptive semantic equalization and joint semantic-radio resource management in dynamic environments.

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